

NOTES

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Transition Metal Complexes of 4-Substituted-2-thiazolylyhydrazones of Salicylaldehyde and 2-Hydroxyacetophenone

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THE communication reports the synthesis and structural studies on the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with some hydrazone derivatives containing thiazole moiety and a OH group near the condensation site, such as 2-salicylideneiminoamino-4-phenylthiazole (SPTH), 2-salicylideneiminoamino-4-bromophenylthiazole (SBPTH), 2- α -methylsalicylideneiminoamino-4-phenylthiazole (MSPTH) and 2- α -methylsalicylideneiminoamino-4-*p*-bromophenylthiazole (MSBPTH).

Experimental

The chemicals used were of reagent grade. The starting materials 2-hydrazino-4-phenylthiazole and 2-hydrazino-4-*p*-bromophenylthiazole were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solution of phenacylbromide and *p*-bromophenacylbromide respectively with thiosemicarbazide. The hydrazones were obtained as coloured solid by refluxing the above hydrazines with salicylaldehyde or 2-hydroxyacetophenone in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol in presence of a few drops of glacial acetic acid.

The complexes were prepared by refluxing hydrated metal(II) chloride with the respective hydrazones in ethanol in 1 : 2 molar ratio in the pH range 8.0–8.5. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether, and dried under reduced pressure (Table 1). They were characterised by elemental analyses, conductance (in DMF), magnetic (at room temperature), ir (KBr) and electronic (dioxane) spectral data.

Results and Discussion

The complexes formulated from the analytical and molar conductance data, support the suggested formulae (Table 1). In the ir spectra of the ligands, the strong and sharp band at $\sim 3\,350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (phenolic OH)¹ disappears in the spectra of all the

complexes, indicating deprotonation of phenolic OH group and coordination to the metal ions through the oxygen atom, which is further substantiated by hypsochromic shift of the phenolic $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ modes around $1\,480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of free ligands by $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes^{2,3}. Besides the above band, a multiple band system occurs at $\sim 3\,200\text{--}2\,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be assigned to the NH and CH vibrations of phenyl groups⁴.

The position of these bands remain practically unaltered in the present complexes, indicating the noninvolvement of imino nitrogen in complexation. The characteristic ir bands in the spectra of the ligands are observed at $\sim 1\,540$ (C=N cyclic), $\sim 1\,320$ (C-N) and $\sim 830\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-S-C) of the thiazole moiety⁵. The position of the former two bands remains unaltered in the present complexes ruling out the possibility of coordination of ring nitrogen of the thiazole moiety. The position of last band shifts to lower frequency by $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes indicating the coordination of ring sulphur atom to the metal ion which may be due to the electronic drainage from the substituents at position-4 by resonance. Besides, other bands occur around $1\,580$ (C=N) and $1\,070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N-N). The former band shifts to lower frequency region by $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the metal complexes indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal ion, whereas the position of the latter band shifts to higher frequency region, further supporting the coordination of azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal ions. The coordination through oxygen and nitrogen atoms of the ligand is further confirmed by the occurrence of new bands at $530\text{--}515$ and $460\text{--}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes which may be assigned to M-O and M-N stretching vibrations respectively⁶.

Besides, the band observed at $\sim 3\,500$ and $\sim 1\,600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to ν_{OH} and δ_{OH} of coordinated or lattice water. However all the complexes lose water when heated to 100° indicating the presence of lattice water molecule.

The room temperature μ_{eff} values lie in the range $4.92\text{--}4.99$, $3.04\text{--}3.18$ and $1.86\text{--}1.9$ B.M. for the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively, in agreement with their octahedral geometry⁷. The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes show bands at $\sim 9\,950$, $19\,960$ and $22\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to octahedral field transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively⁸. The values of transition ratio ν_2/ν_1 , Dq , B and β as calculated by known method⁸, lie in the range $1.9\text{--}2.01$, $1\,128\text{--}1\,184\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $805.76\text{--}945.83\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.83\text{--}0.87$ respectively, providing further evidence for

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis%: Found/(Calcd.)			ΔM $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ mol ⁻¹
			M	N	S	
SPTH	Pale yellow	200	—	10.77 (10.88)	14.38 (14.28)	—
MSPH	Grey	196	—	10.40 (10.36)	13.51 (13.59)	—
SBPTH	Grey	208	—	8.34 (8.41)	11.18 (11.19)	—
MSBPTH	Black	210	—	8.22 (8.24)	10.81 (10.82)	—
[Cu(SPT) ₂].2H ₂ O	Bluish green	230	9.24 (9.23)	12.20 (12.21)	9.29 (9.30)	7.2
Cu(MSPT) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Greenish grey	250	8.84 (8.85)	11.69 (11.70)	8.92 (8.91)	12.6
[Cu(SBPT) ₂].2H ₂ O	Olive green	236	7.48 (7.49)	9.90 (9.91)	7.56 (7.55)	8.3
[Cu(MSBPT) ₂].2H ₂ O	Bluish black	200	7.24 (7.25)	9.58 (9.59)	7.32 (7.31)	11.2
[Ni(SPT) ₂].H ₂ O	Brown	250	8.82 (8.83)	12.62 (12.63)	9.64 (9.62)	5.7
[Ni(MSPT) ₂].H ₂ O	Greenish yellow	250	8.43 (8.44)	12.07 (12.09)	9.20 (9.21)	13.2
[Ni(SBPT) ₂].H ₂ O	Grey	240	7.10 (7.11)	10.19 (10.18)	7.75 (7.76)	10.3
[Ni(MSBPT) ₂].H ₂ O	Chocolate	210	7.12 (7.10)	10.16 (10.17)	7.76 (7.75)	14.1
[Co(SPT) ₂].H ₂ O	Brown	250	8.84 (8.85)	12.62 (12.63)	9.63 (9.62)	7.9
[Co(MSPT) ₂].H ₂ O	Greenish yellow	250	8.46 (8.47)	12.09 (12.08)	9.21 (9.20)	14.3
[Co(SBPT) ₂].H ₂ O	Leaf green	235	7.12 (7.14)	10.17 (10.18)	7.6 (7.7)	12.6
[Co(MSBPT) ₂].H ₂ O	Greenish blue	220	6.91 (6.90)	9.83 (9.84)	7.51 (7.50)	11.4

octahedral geometry. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes are consistent with tetragonal geometry showing bands at ~8 600, ~10 200, ~15 000 and 24 000 cm⁻¹ assignable to ³B_{1g}→³E_g, ³B_{1g}→³B_{2g}, ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively⁶. From the maxima of the component bands and using expression derived on the basis of crystal field approximation, the various tetragonal parameters such as D_t, Dq^E and Dq^A have been calculated and their values lie in the range 189.7–265.14, 1 027–1 086 and 606–695 cm⁻¹ respectively. The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show a broad asymmetric ligand field band at ~14 000–15 000 cm⁻¹ along with a CT band at ~26 000 cm⁻¹. The ligand field band can be assigned to the transition ²E_g→²T_{2g} in a distorted octahedral field under D_{4h} symmetry.

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